

9.2 Guidelines for GEP Impact Evaluation

Document Data	
Report Title	Guidelines for GEP Impact Evaluation
Author(s)	Anell Roos, Mieke Verloo, Inge Bleijenbergh
Other Contributors	
Responsible Project Partner	Radboud University (Katholieke Universiteit Nijmegen)
Due Date	30 06 2019
Delivery Date	28/06/2019
Type	Deliverable
Dissemination Level	Public
Keywords	Evaluation, Design, Impact, Roadmap

History			
Author	Date	Reason for Change	Release
Anell Roos, Mieke Verloo, Inge Bleijenbergh	14/06/2019	First Draft	14/06/2019
Humbert, Anne Laure	26/06/2019	Comments on the first draft	26/06/2019
López Belloso, María	26/06/2019	Comments on the first draft	26/06/2019

Information in this report that may influence other GEARING ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
All	Design and Implementation of GEPs

This project is funded by the EU. This publication has been produced with the financial support of the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824536 The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.

GEARING ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project, therefore, has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers, and work towards real institutional change. This multi-disciplinary, multi-national, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in this space, mentoring activities, awareness-raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

Table of Contents

- GEARING ROLES project** 2
- Executive Summary:**..... 3
- 1. Introduction**..... 4
 - Problem analysis and diagnosis: 4
 - GEP goals and objectives: 6
 - Key performance indicators as set in the project proposal:..... 6
 - A guide to measuring and evaluating the GEP implementation: 7
- 2. Guidelines for Impact Evaluation**..... 7
 - The Relevance of Evaluation:..... 7
 - Sustainability:..... 8
 - The GEP Impact Objectives: 8
 - Objectives of KPI evaluation: 9
 - Criteria to measure impact objectives:..... 10

List of Abbreviations

List of Abbreviations

- EIGE European Institute for Gender Equality
- GEP Gender Equality Plan
- KPI Key Performance Indicator
- WP Work Packages

This project is funded by the EU. This publication has been produced with the financial support of the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824536 The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.

Executive Summary:

This document serves as the main guidelines for the evaluation of the GEARING ROLES project (Grant Agreement Nr.: 824536), to be used during the whole implementation period. It describes the rationale and the details of the Impact Evaluation (9.2).

1. Introduction¹

As a project, GEARING-Roles sets out to make substantial progress in realising gender equality in academic institutions in Europe. GEARING-Roles' main objective is the promotion and realisation of structural change and gender equality in academia and research (Swafs 09-2018: 3). The core element for realising this objective is the GEP - Gender Equality Plan – that each of GEARING-Roles' six implementing institutions will design and implement. These GEPs will be designed combining context specific information with a common reference tool, the GEAR tool developed by EIGE (<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>). The GEPs are designed and developed to tailor fit the respective institution's needs and requirements, leading to a coherent and integrated design logic, building on the GEAR toolkit.

This deliverable will establish and describe the evaluation measures to be used by the Work Package 9 leaders of evaluation and assessment, based at Radboud University Nijmegen. The evaluators recognise and acknowledge that the GEP implementation process may be subjected to various changes, challenges and adaptations throughout its duration. The guidelines in this deliverable thus aim to include attention for such adaptations and changes, anticipating challenges that implementing partners may meet, and address them either directly, or offer tools to mitigate or solve them.

Problem analysis and diagnosis:

The GEPs will be developed by the six implementing partners to promote and realise structural change and gender equality in academia and research. As the primary goal, this includes improving the position of women in academia and research and offering remedial strategies to challenge visible and invisible practices and biases which form obstacles to personal career and research development in academia and research. In order to ensure that the GEPs reach the goals of structural change and gender equality through a successful implementation, and maintain a stronghold in academic and organisational hierarchies beyond the implementation term, an effective evaluation and measurement tool has been developed. The evaluation guidelines developed by Work Package 9 will contribute to the development and implementation of both existing and future gender equality tools.

To successfully challenge traditional gender roles, including women's unequal work representation and the gendered hierarchy within academia, Key Performance Indicators², as described in Swafs 09-2018, will serve to evaluate the implementing partners in their implementation of the GEPs by highlighting objectives to meet throughout and by the end of its four year run. While the proposal sets a clear number of KPIs to be met by the end of the implementation term, the applicability and feasibility of the

¹ This text is similar for the deliverables 9.1, 9.2, and 9.3 because they share a common introduction, and a common goal: the evaluation of the GEPs designed and implemented by six GEARING-Roles consortium members.

² Hereafter referred to as KPIs.

KPIs at each implementing partner must be taken into consideration. Positioning and assessing the achievement of the KPIs aims to support the development of an integrated GEP design logic (Swafs 09-2018: 38) which utilises evaluation and assessment indicators to measure if the GEP is an effective tool to challenge deeply entrenched notions on gender roles and identities, and shift approaches to workplace equality.

GEP goals and objectives:

Following the Swafs 09-2018 (p3-5) proposal, individual GEPs have as their goal the fulfilment and achievement of four main objectives, as explained below:

- a) Female career progression: to remove all barriers that may impede a woman's career path and subsequent success.
- b) Leadership and decision making: to address gender imbalances in the representation, processes, and the promotion of women leadership in research institutions.
- c) Education and research: to promote gender mainstreaming in research (especially in STEM), by including a gender perspective in research programmes, and supporting women's scientific careers.
- d) Promotion of gender equality in research organisations and reinforcing the European Research Area (ERA): to disseminate frameworks and institutional gender assessments and evaluation strategies to establish commitment to gender equality in European organisations, and build sustainable long-term gender equality networks.

Key performance indicators as set in the project proposal:

The Gender Equality Plan Goals and Objectives will be measures with an agreed upon set of KPIs. These KPIs link to the four objectives of the GEARING-Roles project.

For the first expected impact, namely an increase in the participation of women in research and innovation and improvement of their careers prospects, the KPIs are:

- (1) 60 female researchers participating in mentoring programmes.
- (2) 100 participatory Career Development Plans completed.
- (3) Transfer of good practice in HR recruitment processes: at least 12 lessons learnt and shared, 6 examples of good practice adopted by the other institution.

For the second expected impact, which is an improvement of the gender balance in decision-making bodies in research, the KPIs are:

- (1) 10% increase in the representation of women in decision making bodies in relation with baseline assessment at different ranks.
- (2) 6 action plans developed with elements to include leadership and female participation in decision making.
- (3) Data collection on increasing awareness.
- (4) Number of questionnaires contrasting data in relation to base line assessment.

For the third expected impact, which is inclusion, where relevant, of the gender dimension in research content and an increase in the quality and societal relevance of produced knowledge, technologies and innovations, the KPIs are:

- (1) 75 people trained (sex disaggregated and ideally broken down to permanent and temporary staff).
- (2) 80% participation satisfaction with training (exit questionnaires).
- (3) Number of courses with gender training embedded.

For the fourth expected impact, which is that the implementation of Gender Equality Plans in the medium to long term will contribute to the achievement of the ERA, the KPIs are:

- (1) 1 training course on the gender dimensions of research per year.
- (2) An increase in the number of researchers working on gender issues.
- (3) Number of projects awarded addressing gender topics.
- (4) Number of dissertations and master theses finished addressing gender topics, and/or in which gender dimensions and women as users are explicitly taken into account.
- (5) Percentage of increase in different disciplines of the underrepresented genders.
- (6) Percentage of increase of the number of female young researchers (grant holders) to the total per each scientific discipline with respect to year 0 of the project.
- (7) Percentage of increase of the number of female researchers to the total per each scientific discipline with respect to year 0 of the project.

A guide to measuring and evaluating the GEP implementation:

The following guidelines are developed by Work Package 9 leaders to help evaluate the design and impact of each implementing partner's GEP, and to refine and contextualise KPIs for their potential to contribute to a successful implementation of GEPs. The guidelines will ensure the continued quality of internal assessment mechanisms to evaluate the GEPs, and will aid in an analysis of the GEPs as key to addressing gender inequality among consortium partners. The report has been divided into three sections, each of which will deal with a specific aspect of the GEP implementation, leading to a coherent and logical strategic plan.

2. Guidelines for Impact Evaluation

The Relevance of Evaluation:

The design of the six GEPs will serve to bring about structural change and gender equality across research and academic institutions. The Work Package 9 leaders will observe and analyse the transformation processes at both an individual and institutional level, whereby shifts in organisational and institutional culture and the behaviour of the academic community can contribute to, or hinder transformation. The prioritisation of four goals and objectives of the GEARING Roles project remains crucial to achieving structural gender equality, and will be observable through the utilisation of the GEP evaluation. The impact evaluation will shed light on how the GEP has affected the research, education,

and organisational aspects of each institution, and how beneficiaries experience proposed and implemented changes with regard to their personal career development, education and research efforts. The experiences of change agents and beneficiaries are inherent to further developments in (gendered) organisational policy as they provide indicators for weaknesses in gender equality plans to be addressed, strengths in these strategies and action plans to be enhanced, and opportunities for improvement in both the design and implementation of GEPs.

Sustainability:

The impact evaluation aims to establish to which degree the GEPs are successful in reaching goals and objectives by evaluating the progress towards achieving the KPIs, and by assessing the implementation process as a whole. Additionally, this leads to examining the results of the GEP implementation with the aim of assessing the best way of making them sustainable beyond the duration of the project. To enhance and secure the sustainability of the project requires resources to be in place on a permanent basis to ensure that gender equality remains a priority within the organisational structure.

As part of the GEP process, new working relationships, known as procedural success, may be established between relevant stakeholders and partners, regardless of the level of achievement of the objectives of the GEARING Roles project. This procedural success is included in the impact evaluation. By including attention for procedural success, there is attention for the development and passing of procedures and regulations within the GEP implementing partners which could lead to sustainable structural change and gender equality. The establishment of relationships to further and sustain systematic change transcends the results from various gender equality programmes and initiatives. Going beyond procedural success, the project's adaptability is crucial for sustainability. The project's adaptability can be measured by its ability to foresee potential problems and obstacles and find suitable solutions to these obstacles. If applicable, the problems and their solutions must be discussed and analysed.

The GEP Impact Objectives:

The *ex post* impact evaluation aims at assessing to what degree both the short-term and long-term GEP objectives were met, in conjunction with an evaluation of the level of the project's KPI achievement. The impact evaluation will call for measurement and reporting of the KPIs' achievement every 6-12 months in order to evaluate the quality and feasibility of GEP implementation. Furthermore, the *ex post* impact evaluation will contribute to an understanding of the sustainability of the GEP beyond the implementation duration. It is expected that partners are able to show progress in achieving the goals and objectives of the GEARING-Roles project throughout the four year trajectory and not simply at the conclusion. Additionally, the *ex post* evaluation will measure how these GEPs have affected change, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended, at the organisational level of the GEP implementing institution.

Starting from the foundation of the four primary GEP objectives, the impact evaluation objectives are:

- a) The removal of, or development of initiatives to remove, structural barriers and obstacles to women's academic and scientific career progression, and a tangible improvement of women's chances and success within research and academia.
- b) An increase in the number of women at the level of teacher, student, and researcher, with an emphasis on women in leadership positions. This includes an increase of women in management structures of educational institutes and strategies to promote their inclusion.
- c) Education and research: the integration of a gender dimension in research, STEM, and knowledge production has been made visible and has increased, as a result of curricula restructuring and staff trainings.
- d) The achievement of the ERA has been significantly bolstered and promoted through the GEP implementation.

While the evaluation of these four objectives will be monitored throughout the GEARING roles project, a final reflection on the six GEPs as instruments to foster structural change and gender equality will be part of the final *ex post* evaluation conducted by Work Package 9 during the fourth year. This reflection will also aim to evaluate the EIGE GEAR tool as an effective tool for gender equality, including its tools for design, structure, and implementation strategies, in order to advance its future applicability.

Objectives of KPI evaluation:

The KPIs which were developed for use in the GEP process, and which will serve as evaluation criteria *ex post*, will serve the following goals throughout the implementation:

- a) To monitor the subjective success of the GEP; thus how well the actors (at all levels) respond to the GEP, either in its entirety, or to specific components.
- b) To monitor how well the programme is being implemented at each partner institution.
- c) To monitor if the GEP is reaching its intended objectives, and if not, why.
- d) To shed light on decision-making processes at each partner institution with regard to the prioritisation of needs and decision-making.

To enable the realisation of the full potential of the KPIs, each implementing partner should be able to show and explain any achievements regarding the KPIs, any emerging contextual factors impacting on these achievements, in order for them to be evaluated for their success and their potential to be successful. Interviews will be used as a method for this, combined with surveys. While partner institutions bear the responsibility of assessing the context for each GEP, Work Package 9 is responsible for the evaluation of the design of the GEP, including the viability of each KPI.

The KPIs, as formulated in the GEARING-Roles project, are currently broad in their scope and applicability, leading to two important considerations. First, it should be assessed whether each KPI has the potential to be met at the respective institutions, and in the case it is not, each implementing

partner's statement on the reasons for this inability need to be provided. Secondly, should the KPIs be assessed as partially unattainable, an analysis must determine which consequences would result from a partial fulfilment of the KPIs in each respective implementing partner, i.e. is progress still being made, or do problems and discrepancies arise?

An annual comparative analysis will aid in evaluating the KPIs as a model to be used in future projects. Such an analysis will include comparisons between implementing institutions, and between moments in time.

Criteria to measure impact objectives:

The starting point to measure the impact of the GEP will be the diagnosis conducted under WP 3.

a) Effectiveness Indicators:

These indicators will measure to which extent the intended goals of the GEP were reached. The KPIs will serve as the main foundation to measure the GEP's effectiveness as a tool for gender equality. Effectiveness measures will investigate whether or not the results obtained from the implementation strategies correlate with the policy objectives of the GEARING roles project, and to what degree the GEP was effectively implemented in an inefficient system, or ineffectively implemented in an efficient system.

Effectiveness indicators will thus measure:

- (1) Changes in the achievement of KPIs throughout the GEP implementation, up to its completion, compared to its start.
- (2) Whether the GEP interventions and activities were responsible for changes observed.
- (3) If these changes comply or deviate from the proposed objectives in the initial proposal, and in what sense they differ.

Closely tied in with measuring how well targets are achieved, is the consideration of how actors involved in meeting the objectives of the GEP are affected. We aim to understand for whom the objectives were realised during the GEP implementation, and who benefits from the sustainability and the evaluation of objectives as successful or unsuccessful. We will do this through biannual interviews with core actors in the GEP implementation, and through surveys on a wider group of beneficiaries.

b) Efficiency Indicators:

These indicators will measure how the actions and activities of the GEP implementing partners have been converted into tangible results, and whether the GEP was effective in reaching its objectives using the least possible amount of resources within a set of budgetary and resource (human, financial, procedural) constraints.

The primary indicators to measure GEP efficiency can be listed below:

- 1) Have the objectives and KPIs been achieved to their fullest potential within these parameters?
A main concern for the continuation of the GEP project and other similar gender equality projects is whether the quality of the implementation and the results were adversely affected by budgetary and/or resource restraints as opposed to other factors.
- 2) How may the GEP become more efficient utilising different approaches, and so deliver similar or even better results? If applicable, how was this manifested?

Evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of the GEPs involves the actors in the project, including the beneficiaries, project leadership, and male staff, and is influenced by how these actors define and perceive their own experiences and satisfaction within the GEP. This includes their satisfaction with the GEP as a whole, or to what degree particular components received great support than others. If there are differences, what led to this preference?

c) Objective Impact Indicators:

This refers to the structural change in institutes of science and academia aimed at realising gender equality as foundational pillar of cultural, social, and economic transformation. We will assess to what degree substantial and/or procedural success have been achieved, with the aim of facilitating and upholding the implementation of new programmes and policies as key to achieving gender equality.

